

Thermodynamic Parameters and Stability Constants of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Rh(III) and Pt(IV) Complexes with Diaminoacetyl Urea

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Manuscript received 21 August 1978, revised 9 November 1979, accepted 13 May 1980

The stability constants of the complexes of copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II), zinc(II), palladium(II), rhodium(III) and platinum(IV) with diaminoacetyl urea are reported. The order of decreasing stability of divalent metal is $\text{Pd}^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+}$. The stepwise changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) values for complexation are evaluated in different ionic strengths (0.15M, 0.125M, 0.1M and 0.075M) and at different temperatures ($25 \pm 0.02^\circ$ and $30 \pm 0.02^\circ$). The standard ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° are also calculated at zero ionic strength. The nature of the co-valent bonding in the complexes have been discussed in detail.

ALTHOUGH stability constants values for interaction of metal ions with complexing ligands are generally reported in literature, there are few corresponding thermodynamic constants ΔG , ΔH and ΔS values available. Such data are useful in evaluating the relative importance of thermodynamic constants in determining the magnitude of stability constant and understanding the factors which contributes to the complex formation.

Diaminoacetyl urea (hereafter abbreviated as DAAU) forms complexes with many metal ions^{1,2,3}. The reagent has been used for spectrophotometric study of metal ions. In view of the great potentialities of the NH_2 group as analytical reagent, it is desirable to study its physico-chemical aspects.

Structure I : DAAU

In the present communication, the stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of the complexes of copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II), zinc(II), palladium(II), rhodium(III) and platinum(IV) with DAAU in aqueous solution have been studied in different ionic strengths (0.15M, 0.125M, 0.10M and 0.075M) and at temperatures. ($25 \pm 0.02^\circ$ and $30 \pm 0.02^\circ$).

Experimental

DAAU was prepared by the procedure described in an earlier paper¹. The stock solution of metal ions were prepared by dissolving copper sulphate, nickel sulphate, cobalt sulphate, zinc sulphate, palladium chloride, rhodium chloride and chloroplatinic acid. Sodium hydroxide (0.1M) solution was made by dissolving AR(BDH) NaOH pellets in carbondioxide free distilled water and was standardised with standard solution of oxalic acid.

The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling the nitrogen gas through the solution. The pH measurements were carried out with the solution maintaining four different ionic strengths (0.15M, 0.125M, 0.1M and 0.075M) which were achieved by adding requisite quantity of 0.1 M sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid.

Solution mixture containing (a) acid (0.01M perchloric acid + 0.1M sodium perchlorate), (b) ligand (mixture 'a' and 25 ml of 0.1M DAAU) and (c) complex (mixture 'b' and 5 ml of 0.01M metal solution) were taken and total volume was kept 50 ml. The mixtures (a), (b) and (c) were separately titrated against standard 0.1M sodium hydroxide.

pH measurements were done by Phillips pH meter using glass calomel electrode assembly at constant temperatures $25 (\pm 0.02)^\circ$ and $30 (\pm 0.02)^\circ$.

Method and Calculations: The stability constants were determined, using the Bjerrum-Calvin technique^{4,5} as adopted by Irving⁶ and Rossotti⁷.

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Thermodynamic Constant :

Thermodynamic constant values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS), accompanying complexation, have been calculated with the help of standard equations.

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln \beta$$

and
$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

The values of ΔH were calculated at each temperature interval by the relationship

$$\Delta H = \frac{2.303 R T_1 T_2 \log K_2 / K_1}{(T_2 - T_1)}$$

Results

The values of $\bar{n}_H$ (the number of proton attached to the ligand), $\bar{n}$ (the number of ligand molecule attached to central metal ions) and P_L (negative logarithm of the anion of the ligand) were calculated by using Irving and Rossotti expressions⁷ :

The DAAU showed a maxima of one for $\bar{n}_H$, the dissociation constant (pK) of the ligand was calculated from pH value corresponding to $\bar{n}_H = 0.5$ at different ionic strengths and different temperatures. The formation curves were drawn by plotting $\bar{n}$ and P_L values. The stepwise formation constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated from the P_L values corresponding $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively at different temperatures (25°

and 30°) and at various ionic strengths ($\mu = 0.15 M, 0.125 M, 0.10 M$ and $0.075 M$).

The thermodynamic dissociation constants and formation constants were obtained by determination at various ionic strengths, followed by extrapolation to zero ionic strength^{2,1}. The sum of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ at $\mu = 0$ gives the value of $\log \beta$ at $\mu = 0$. The values of $\log \beta$ (overall concentration formation constants) were likewise extrapolated to zero ionic strength. The thermodynamic parameters that were calculated from stability constants are listed in Table 3.

Discussion

The dissociation constants of the ligand DAAU and stability constants of the complexes obtained at different temperatures ($25 \pm 0.02^\circ$ and $30 \pm 0.02^\circ$) and various ionic strengths are given in Tables 1 and 2. From the

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF LIGAND DAAU

Ionic strength (μ)	pK_1 at $25^\circ C$	pK_1 at $30^\circ C$
0.15 M	9.65	9.50
0.125 M	9.70	9.60
0.1 M	9.80	9.70
0.075 M	9.85	9.75
0.0 M	10.05	9.95

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL CHELATES OF DAAU

Metal ions	Stability Constants	Temperature $25^\circ C$					Temperature $30^\circ C$				
		$\mu = 0.15M$	$0.12M$	$0.10M$	$0.075M$	$\mu = 0$	$\mu = 0.15M$	$0.12M$	$0.10M$	$0.075M$	$\mu = 0$
Cu(II)	$\log K_1$	10.06	10.12	10.25	10.32	10.70	9.82	9.85	9.95	10.20	10.40
	$\log K_2$	6.31	6.38	6.50	6.72	7.00	6.01	6.11	6.15	6.20	6.45
	$\log \beta$	16.37	16.50	16.75	17.04	17.70	15.83	15.96	16.10	16.40	16.85
Ni(II)	$\log K_1$	9.72	9.80	10.05	10.20	10.45	9.52	9.60	9.65	9.82	9.90
	$\log K_2$	5.86	5.90	5.95	6.10	6.15	5.75	5.80	5.80	5.85	5.85
	$\log \beta$	15.58	15.70	16.00	16.30	16.60	15.27	15.40	15.45	15.67	15.75
Co(II)	$\log K_1$	9.80	9.82	9.90	10.10	10.30	9.65	9.80	9.95	10.00	10.05
	$\log K_2$	5.95	6.00	6.15	6.20	6.40	6.00	6.10	6.20	6.25	6.45
	$\log \beta$	15.75	15.82	16.35	16.30	16.70	15.65	15.90	16.15	16.25	16.50
Zn(II)	$\log K_1$	9.95	10.05	10.15	10.20	10.50	9.85	9.90	10.00	10.10	10.30
	$\log K_2$	6.00	6.10	6.20	6.25	6.45	5.85	5.95	6.15	6.20	6.40
	$\log \beta$	15.95	16.15	16.35	16.45	16.95	15.70	15.85	16.15	16.30	16.70
Pd(II)	$\log K_1$	10.55	10.60	10.75	10.80	11.15	10.00	10.10	10.25	10.70	10.85
	$\log K_2$	6.40	6.45	6.50	6.65	6.70	6.35	6.40	6.50	6.52	6.60
	$\log \beta$	16.95	17.05	17.25	17.45	17.85	16.35	16.50	16.75	17.22	17.45
Rh(III)	$\log K_1$	9.55	9.60	9.75	9.95	10.20	9.35	9.30	9.65	9.65	10.10
	$\log K_2$	4.85	5.00	5.15	5.30	5.75	4.75	4.90	5.00	5.10	5.45
	$\log \beta$	14.40	14.60	14.90	15.25	15.95	14.10	14.40	14.65	14.95	15.55
Pt(IV)	$\log K_1$	10.80	10.85	10.90	11.05	11.10	10.65	10.75	10.75	10.95	11.10
	$\log K_2$	6.52	6.55	6.70	6.85	6.95	6.30	6.42	6.45	6.60	6.85
	$\log \beta$	17.82	17.40	17.60	17.90	18.05	16.95	17.17	17.20	17.50	17.95

structure of DAAU it reveals that it has two-NH₂ groups and two NH groups between two -C=O groups. The liberation of hydrogen from NH₂ group is more possible than -NH group. At higher pH value, the alkali reaction liberates both hydrogen ions simultaneously. Thus only one protonation constants is expected upto certain range of pH value. Similar observations were also reported in case of biuret⁸. The stability order of the divalent metal complexes in all ionic strengths studied here is Pd²⁺ > Cu²⁺ > Zn²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Ni²⁺, except for cobalt ion, the order is the same as in Irving Williams series⁹. Such type of abnormal behaviour by cobalt were also reported earlier^{10,11}. Johnston and Freiser¹² reported similar observations in their investigations on metal complexes of 8-OH-2-methyl quinoline. The higher stability of the cobalt complex was attributed to higher oxidation state of cobalt in the complex. The oxidation of Co(II) to Co(III) has taken place in the present investigation during complex formation. Such behaviour of cobalt with DAAU is already communicated³. The variation of the stability of the complexes of divalent metal ions may be represented by plotting log β against atomic number and second ionization potential of the metal (Fig. 1.) Such correlation, were made by

Fig. 1. The plot of log β (at μ=0) vs atomic number of divalent metal ion and second ionization potential in volt of M²⁺.
 ○ - ○ log β vs atomic number at 25°C
 △ - △ log β vs atomic number at 30°C
 ● - ● log β vs 2nd ionization potential at 25°C
 ▲ - ▲ log β vs 2nd ionization potential at 30°C

Calvin and Melchior¹³ for the formation of metal chelates of 5-salicylaldehyde sulphonate. The low value of stability constant of Zn²⁺ than Cu²⁺ may be explained on the basis of the following factors: (a) d-orbital,

which is not taking part in homopolar bond formation, (b) ionic radii and (c) due to higher charge density of electron around the metal ion. The plot of χ_m (electronegativity of metal) against log β (Fig. 2) shows

Fig. 2. The plot of electronegativity (χ_m) vs overall stability constant (log β).

○ - ○ at 25°C
 △ - △ at 30°C

roughly a linear relationship. It may be inferred that the greater stability of metal complex with increasing χ_m value and metal ligand bond would be more covalent. Similar observations have been reported by Vanuiter¹⁴ and Sebin¹⁵. The plot of log β against reciprocal of ionic radii of transition metals ($\frac{1}{r_{crust}}$) (Fig. 3), show that the ligand forms most unstable

Fig. 3. The plot of reciprocal of ionic radii vs log β (at μ=0)
 ○ - ○ at 25°C
 △ - △ at 30°C

complex with nickel(II) metal and stabler complex with copper II) than other divalent transition metals. The presence of π bond of M-L may be explained on the basis of high positive value of the log K₁/K₂. Similar results have been reported in literature⁴ and can be assumed to be due to a combination of factors such as static, steric hindrance.

The standard ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° values which are obtained from extrapolated value of the stability constants to zero ionic strength are listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC CONSTANTS OF METAL INTERACTION OF DAAU

Metal Ion		ΔG° (Free energy) K cal/mole at $\mu=0$		ΔH° (enthalpy) at $\mu=0$ K cal/mole	ΔS° (entropy) at $\mu=0$ K cal/ degree mole
		25°C	30 C		
Cu ²⁺	log K ₁	-14.59	-14.41	-24.79	-0.15470
	log K ₂	9.54	-9.94	-45.45	
	log β	-24.13	-23.36	-70.24	
Ni ²⁺	log K ₁	-14.38	-13.72	-45.45	-0.15976
	log K ₂	-8.38	-8.11	-24.79	
	log β	-22.63	-21.83	-70.24	
Co ²⁺	log K ₁	-14.04	-13.93	-20.65	+0.02095
	log K ₂	-8.72	-8.94	+4.13	
	log β	-22.77	-22.87	-16.52	
Zn ²⁺	log K ₁	-14.31	-14.28	-16.52	+0.00825
	log K ₂	-8.79	-8.87	-4.13	
	log β	-23.11	-23.15	-20.65	
Pd ²⁺	log K ₁	-15.20	-15.04	-24.79	-0.02923
	log K ₂	-9.13	-9.15	-8.26	
	log β	-24.33	-24.19	-35.05	
Rh ²⁺	log K ₁	-13.90	-14.00	-8.26	-0.03792
	log K ₂	-7.84	-7.55	-24.79	
	log β	-21.75	-21.56	-33.05	
Pt ²⁺	log K ₁	-15.13	-15.39	-0.0	+0.05485
	log K ₂	-9.47	-9.49	-8.26	
	log β	-24.60	-24.88	-8.26	

It is of interest to compare the stability constants value with standard free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°). The linear relationships are obtained (Figs. 4,5,6). The enthalpy for complex species ΔH° ($\log K_1$) is more negative than the value of ΔH° ($\log$

Fig. 4. The plot of ΔG° vs $\log \beta$ (at $\mu=0$)
 ●—● at 25°C
 ○—○ at 30°C

Fig. 5. The plot of ΔH° vs $\log \beta$ (at $\mu=0$)

Fig. 6. The plot of ΔS° vs $\log \beta$

K_2). The enthalpy corresponding to the formation of complexes are exothermic. There is a regular change in the value of ΔH° for complexes in series of divalent metal ion, except in case of cobalt complex in which ΔH° ($\log K_2$) value is positive. The abnormal behaviour of cobalt is already reported above. A positive value of ΔH° ($\log K_2$) of cobalt may be due to high heat of hydration. To study the bonding nature of the complexes it is necessary to observe the relation between ionic radii of metal against thermodynamic parameters. The plot of the thermodynamic parameters ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° against $\frac{1}{r}$ (ionic radii) of divalent transition metal, (Figs. 7,8,9), show good linear relationship. Thus entropy of the complex species for divalent metal ion studied are proportional to the reciprocal of their ionic radii. Martell¹⁶ has suggested a dependence linear relationship between ΔS° and $\frac{1}{r}$ for divalent metals. Similar observations were reported by Stavely¹⁷ for EDTA complexes. This indicates the predominant role of electrostatic forces involved in the ion-association processes, a fact which is in harmony with Bjerrum original ion pair concept. Martell and Khan¹⁸ have studied similar linearity by plot of ΔS° against $(r_a+r_c)^{-1}$ where r_a and r_c are the anionic and cationic radii respectively. From Table 3 the relatively small ΔH° values compared with large value of ΔS° indicates entropy as the principal driving force for formation of metal complexes in aqueous solution. The positive value of the entropy in case of cobalt and zinc, reflecting the release of coordinated water molecules from interacting ions because of the partial or complete change of the neutralization. The number of coordinated negative

Fig. 7. The plot of ΔG° vs $1/r$
 A ●—● At temp. 25°C
 B ○—○ At temp. 30°C

Fig. 8. The plot of ΔH° vs $1/r$

Fig. 9. The plot of ΔS° vs $1/r$

donor group (Z_e) and electronegativity of the metal ion (χ_m) have been correlated with the effective radii of metal ion, in the present study. The correlation between effective radius of metal ion and electronega-

tivity as given by equation below, is indicated in Table 4 and illustrated graphically in Fig. 10.

$$r_e = r_p + 0.48 + 0.14Z_e \chi_m$$

TABLE 4—CORRELATION OF THE EFFECTIVE RADIUS OF THE METAL ION WITH ELECTRONEGATIVITY

Divalent metal ion	r_a	χ_M	r_e	$r_e - r_p$
Co	0.72	1.70	2.152	1.45
Ni	0.69	1.75	2.15	1.46
Cu	0.65	1.75	2.11	1.46
Zn	0.74	1.66	2.15	1.41

r_p = Pauling ionic radii, r_e = effective ionic radii (angstrom unit),

χ_M = Electronegativity of metal ion on Allred-Rochow scale.

where r_e is the effective radius of the metal ions, χ_m their electronegativity on the Allred-Rochow¹⁹ scale, and r_p is Pauling crystal radius in angstrom. Such relationship indicates better understanding of covalent nature of the complexes. Such correlations have also been reported in case of adenosine diphosphoric and adnosine monophosphoric acid metal complexes²⁰.

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Fig. 10. Correlation of the effective radius of the metal ion with electronegativity.

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